

D2.4
LOCAL BEHAVIOUR LAW, SCALE CHANGE AND
HOMOGENISATION

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enable

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| Sweden | TI Timet | SVK Sandvik Coromant | SUP Superior National School of Mines of |
| Belgium | MET Metallcadour | TEC Tecnia | LTU Lulea University of Technology |
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Contents

1	Introduction	2
2	Single crystal plasticity models	3
2.1	Phenomenological crystal plasticity models	4
2.2	Physics based crystal plasticity models	5
3	Polycrystal plasticity models	6
3.1	Scale transition rule	6
3.2	Mean-field models	6
3.3	Full-field models	8
3.3.1	Homogenization using FEM	8
3.3.2	Homogenization using FFT	9
4	Applications of polycrystal plasticity model	10
4.1	Determination of material strength	10
4.2	Void growth in polycrystals	12
4.3	Fatigue life	14
4.4	Other applications	14
5	Concluding remark	14

1. Introduction

The continuum crystal plasticity can be used to predict the anisotropic behaviour of the single crystal. Moreover, crystal plasticity can be used to predict the polycrystal behaviour from the knowledge of single crystal behaviour. The structural metals are polycrystalline and each grain has distinct properties from its neighbouring grains. Each grain of the polycrystal deforms by a different amount as compared to its neighbouring grain (Ashby, 1970). The stress and strain fields within the grains of polycrystalline aggregate are highly heterogeneous. These heterogeneities can lead to crack initiation or damage in crystalline solid (Cailletaud et al., 2003b). It is difficult to describe the local behaviour of each grain within the heterogeneous material as the local properties of one grain differs significantly from the other grains. The objective of the micromechanics of the heterogeneous material is to predict the polycrystal behaviour from the knowledge of a constitutive framework for single crystal, grain morphology, and crystallographic texture. The computational homogenization method has been developed to predict the mechanical behaviour of polycrystalline aggregate. Computational homogenization is an important tool to relate microstructure with macroscopic or effective properties of the polycrystal (Cailletaud, 1992; Nemat-Nasser et al., 1996; Cailletaud et al., 2003b,a; Jeulin et al., 2004). Polycrystal homogenization bridge the gap between microscopic and macroscopic behaviour of material by integrating microscopic stress and strain to obtain macroscopic stress and strain in a polycrystal. The macroscopic or effective properties can be found from the geometrical features of the microstructure. Following the pioneering work of Eshelby (Eshelby and Peierls, 1957) several 'mean-field', homogenization models have been developed. The models developed for the linear material are (Kröner, 1958; Hill, 1965; Mori and Tanaka, 1973). Then these models were extended to deal with the non-linearity in material behaviour. Among these models, the elastic self-consistent (SC) modeling arises the most reliable solution to obtains the elastic response of the polycrystal. The SC models predict the effective behaviour by approximation as inclusion embedded in the homogeneous equivalent medium (HEM). The state of each phase is evaluated by approximation as inclusion embedded in the HEM. The phase in the polycrystal consists of grains having the same crystallographic orientation. The linear elastic SC models then extended for visco-plastic f.c.c. polycrystal by Molinari et al. (1987). There are some limitations to SC modeling. The first one is that these models do not take into account local heterogeneity such as grain clustering as these models are based on the average values of grain size, shape, and orientations. The second one is that these models assume the local fields in the grain or phase are constant and therefore cannot be used for the phenomenon such as shear band formation (strain localization) in one or several grains. The third limitation is the large variation on hydrostatic pressure can not be predicted by the mean-field models as it is assumed that the elasticity is constant.

These limitations of SC models can be overcome by using the computation of representative volume element (RVE) of heterogeneous material for boundary value problems under homogeneous boundary conditions. Instead of considering as an inclusion embedded into HEM computations are performed on the volume element having enough grains to regards it as a representative volume element of the polycrystal (Smit et al., 1998).

Fig. 1: Identification of material parameters using RVE simulation (Flipon et al., 2020)

Computation of RVE provides the full heterogeneous stress and strain field inside the grain taking into account the grain boundaries as well therefore these models are also called 'full-field' models. The mean stress and strain computed from these models can be used to compare prediction made by mean-field models. The Computation of RVE regarded as a reference calculation to check the quality of estimation made by the mean-field models (Barbe et al., 2001; Böhm, 2004). Fig. 1 shows the RVE simulation used for the material parameters calibrations from the experimental stress-strain curve for the polycrystal compression test.

The simulation of the mechanical behaviour of polycrystals gained a large amount of attention in the last 3 decades and mature strategies based on the mean-field or full-field models are available nowadays. The objective of the deliverable is to summarise the mean-field and full-field models, scale transition rule, and application of polycrystal homogenization in an industrial context. The outline of this deliverable is as follows. In section 2 phenomenological and physics-based constitutive framework for single crystal is presented. In section 3 polycrystal mean-field and FE models are presented. Applications of the polycrystal models are presented in section 4. Concluding remarks follows in section 5.

The notations used in the deliverable are as follows. Underline $\underline{\mathbf{A}}$ and under-wave bold $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{A}}}$ are respectively for vectors and second-order tensors. The transpose, inverse, inverse of transpose and time derivative are represented as $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{A}}}^T$, $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{A}}}^{-1}$, $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{A}}}^{-T}$ and $\dot{\underline{\underline{\mathbf{A}}}}$ respectively. The contraction product, outer product, dyadic product, and the tensorial product is written as $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{A}}} : \underline{\underline{\mathbf{A}}}$, $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{A}}} \wedge \underline{\underline{\mathbf{A}}}$, $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{A}}} \cdot \underline{\underline{\mathbf{A}}}$ and $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{A}}} \otimes \underline{\underline{\mathbf{A}}}$ respectively.

2. Single crystal plasticity models

The single crystals are of interest in structural materials in the turbine blade and propeller as well as considered as a building block for the polycrystalline materials. The continuum crystal plasticity takes into account the material strain hardening in plastically deforming material due to dislocation glide, dislocation multiplication, and interaction. There are two types of dislocations which are responsible for the strain hardening

in the material. The first one is the statistically stored dislocations (SSDs) which cause the material strain hardening due to random trapping of the dislocations with one another. The second type of dislocations are the geometrically necessary dislocations (GNDs) which are present due to type of geometry, type of loading or the material itself is nonhomogenous. The density of GNDs are associated with the deformation gradient and allows the compatible deformation (Ashby, 1970). The familiar examples of GNDs storage are plastic bending and torsion. In contrast, the dislocation is not geometrically necessary in the tension of a pure single crystal. Even though the dislocation does accumulate and their presence causes the characteristic strain hardening of the material.

The first model that defines the plastic deformation of a single crystal was proposed by Taylor and Elam (1923, 1925). This model was further utilised to analyse the deformation of polycrystal aggregate (Taylor, 1938). The single-crystal model proposed by Taylor was put into continuum framework by Mandel (1965); Hill (1966) for small deformation. The theory, based on the general thermodynamic formulation, was extended for finite deformation by Rice (1971) and Hill and Rice (1972). They used multiplicative decomposition of the total deformation gradient proposed by Lee and Liu (1967). The multiplicative decomposition leads to the following partition of the velocity gradient ($\underline{\mathbf{L}}$) into elastic ($\underline{\mathbf{L}}^e$) and plastic parts ($\underline{\mathbf{L}}^p$).

$$\underline{\mathbf{L}} = \underline{\mathbf{L}}^e + \underline{\mathbf{L}}^p, \quad \underline{\mathbf{L}} = \dot{\underline{\mathbf{F}}} \cdot \underline{\mathbf{F}}^{-1} = \dot{\underline{\mathbf{F}}}^e \cdot \underline{\mathbf{F}}^{e-1} + \underline{\mathbf{F}}^e \cdot \dot{\underline{\mathbf{F}}}^p \cdot \underline{\mathbf{F}}^{p-1} \cdot \underline{\mathbf{F}}^{e-1} \quad (1)$$

The plastic deformation takes place through the slip of dislocations on prescribed lattice slip planes with normal $\underline{\mathbf{n}}^\alpha$ along prescribed lattice slip direction $\underline{\mathbf{m}}^\alpha$:

$$\dot{\underline{\mathbf{F}}}^p \cdot \underline{\mathbf{F}}^{p-1} = \sum_{\alpha=1}^N \dot{\gamma}^\alpha (\underline{\mathbf{m}}^\alpha \otimes \underline{\mathbf{n}}^\alpha) \quad (2)$$

2.1. Phenomenological crystal plasticity models

Crystal plasticity uses the phenomenological flow rule to evaluate the slip rate and internal variables. The problems associated with the rate-independent crystal plasticity are overcome after (Anand and Kothari, 1996), the viscoplastic formulation for monotonic loading was introduced by (Peirce et al., 1982).

The evolution of slip rate ($\dot{\gamma}^\alpha$) is given by the flow rule as follows

$$\dot{\gamma}^\alpha = \dot{\gamma}_0 \left(\frac{|\tau^\alpha|}{\tau_c^\alpha} \right)^n \text{sign}(\tau^\alpha) \quad (3)$$

where τ^α is the resolved shear stress, τ_c^α is the critical resolved shear stress (CRSS) on each slip system, $\dot{\gamma}_0^\alpha$ reference strain rate. The CRSS (τ_c^α) corresponds to minimum value of resolved shear stress (τ^α) to trigger plastic glide. n is the strain rate sensitivity. The evolution of CRSS is given by

$$\dot{\tau}_c^\alpha = \sum_{s=1}^N h^{\alpha s} |\dot{\gamma}^\alpha| \quad (4)$$

where $h^{\alpha s}$ is the hardening matrix. $h^{\alpha s}$ is the latent hardening matrix and $h^{\alpha \alpha}$ is the self-hardening matrix.

The extension of the above phenomenological flow rule to include kinematic hardening is done by [Méric et al. \(1991\)](#); [Cailletaud \(1992\)](#). The flow rule in the visco-plastic framework, together with the classical Schmid law to trigger dislocation glide and also with kinematic hardening variable is given as

$$\dot{\gamma}^{\alpha} = \left\langle \frac{|\tau^{\alpha} - x^{\alpha}| - \tau_c^{\alpha}}{K} \right\rangle^n \text{sign}(\tau^{\alpha} - x^{\alpha}) \quad (5)$$

where τ^{α} is the resolved shear stress, x^{α} is the kinematic hardening variable, τ_c^{α} is the isotropic hardening variable (CRSS). Higher value of power n and lower value of K lead to an almost ideal elastic–plastic behaviour in a given strain rate range. The identification of such a phenomenological flow rule can be found in [Méric et al. \(1991\)](#).

A non-linear hardening rule accounts for the evolution of the hardening variable that completes the crystal plasticity constitutive model.

$$\tau_c^{\alpha} = \tau_0 + q \sum_{s=1}^N h^{s\alpha} (1 - \exp(-bv^s)) \quad (6)$$

In Eq. (6), τ_0 is the initial critical resolved shear stress, $h^{s\alpha}$ is the hardening matrix accounting for self ($s = \alpha$) and latent hardening ($s \neq \alpha$), v^s is the cumulative plastic strain, q and b are the phenomenological constants. The back-stress (x^{α}) evolution is given as following

$$\dot{x}^{\alpha} = c\dot{\gamma}^{\alpha} - d|\dot{\gamma}^{\alpha}| \quad (7)$$

where c and d are constants which defines the hardening rate.

2.2. Physics based crystal plasticity models

The Physics-based plasticity models give a strong physical connection with the microscopic mechanism of plastic deformation by introducing microscopic internal variables such as dislocation density. The first step in the physics-based model is the relationship between shear rate and dislocation density as given by Orwan equation

$$\dot{\gamma}^{\alpha} = \rho_m^{\alpha} b^{\alpha} \bar{v}^{\alpha} \quad (8)$$

where ρ_m^{α} is the mobile dislocation density, b^{α} is the Burgers vector and \bar{v}^{α} is the average velocity of dislocations. The driving force for the dislocation motion is the resolved shear stress. Athermal barrier for the dislocation motion is introduced by athermal CRSS which is proportional to dislocation density as follows ([Taylor, 1938](#))

$$\tau_a \propto \mu b \sqrt{\rho} \quad (9)$$

where μ is the shear modulus.

The strain hardening based on dislocation density based takes into account the hindrance to the dislocation motion is due to the interaction of the dislocations. The evolution of critical resolved shear stress (CRSS) τ_c^α based on scalar dislocation density is given (Kubín et al., 2008) as follows:

$$\tau_c^\alpha = \tau_0 + \mu \sqrt{\sum_{s=1}^N a^{\alpha s} \rho^s} \quad (10)$$

where τ_0 is the initial CRSS, μ is the shear modulus, $a^{\alpha s}$ is the interaction matrix describing long-range interaction between the dislocations and ρ^s is the scalar dislocation density. The evolution of dislocation density is given by the following equation

$$\dot{\rho}^\alpha = |\dot{\gamma}^\alpha| \left(\frac{\sqrt{\sum_{s=1}^N b^{\alpha s} \rho^s}}{k} - G_c \rho^\alpha \right) \quad (11)$$

The first term in the above equation corresponds to dislocation generation and the second term corresponds to dislocation annihilation. $b^{\alpha s}$ matrix describes the dislocation interaction, k is the parameter proportional to the number of obstacles crossed by a dislocation before being immobilized, G_c is the critical distance controlling the annihilation of dislocations with opposite signs.

3. Polycrystal plasticity models

3.1. Scale transition rule

The scale transition rule links the mean local stress ($\boldsymbol{\sigma}^g$) to macroscopic stress ($\boldsymbol{\sigma}$), mean viscoplastic strain ($\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^p$) to local viscoplastic strain ($\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{pg}$), here g represent the grain or phase. Once the behaviour of the single crystal is defined one has to find the behaviour of a polycrystal aggregate. Phases in the polycrystal are defined according to crystal orientations, phases having the same Euler angle are all within the same class. The homogenization models proposed for the polycrystals differs in their scale transition rule to predict the local stresses and strains. Several authors made a hypothesis for the strain redistribution within the phases. Taylor (Taylor, 1938) assumes a uniform plastic strain, $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{pg} = \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^p$; the assumption of uniform plastic strain is somewhat crude; it fails when the experiment shows the evidence of plastic strain heterogeneity like in uniaxial compression of f.c.c. metals. Lin-Taylor (Lin, 1957) assume an uniform total strain, $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^g = \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$. All the uniform strain theories satisfy the compatibility condition but do not satisfy the equilibrium at the grain boundaries.

3.2. Mean-field models

Kröner's (Kröner, 1958) model gives an elastic accommodation,

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}^g = \boldsymbol{\sigma} + 2\mu(1 - \beta)(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^p - \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{pg}) \quad (12)$$

with

$$\beta = \frac{2(4 - 5\nu)}{15(1 - \nu)} \quad (13)$$

β only depends on the Poisson's ratio and roughly around 0.5.

Kröner's model gives very high value of internal stresses due to assumption of elastic accommodation $2\mu(1 - \beta)(\underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}^p - \underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}^{pg})$ via large value of shear modulus μ . The approximation can be made to take into account the plastic accommodation by replacing the elastic shear modulus by adequate elastoplastic modulus.

A more precise formulation can be derived from Hill's approximation (Hill, 1965) by an assumption of an isotropic elastoplastic interaction between one grain and the matrix of other grains. The self-consistent approximation which considers as each phase an ellipsoid in a homogeneous equivalent medium. Hill describes the self-consistent approximation by isotropic elastoplastic accommodation as follows

Let $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{L}}}^g$ and $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{L}}}$ are the fourth-order tensors of incremental moduli of individual grain and whole aggregate respectively. The relation between stress and strain rate in the individual grain and whole aggregate respectively is given by

$$\dot{\underline{\underline{\sigma}}}^g = \underline{\underline{\mathbf{L}}}^g \dot{\underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}}^g, \quad \dot{\underline{\underline{\sigma}}} = \underline{\underline{\mathbf{L}}} \dot{\underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}} \quad (14)$$

Let $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{L}}}^*$ be the 'constraint' tensor associated with $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{L}}} : \underline{\underline{\mathbf{L}}}^*$ as defined from the relation between the uniform strain-rate of an ellipsoidal void in the matrix and the traction-rate which is needed to perform this operation; then $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{L}}}^*$ depends only on the tensor $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{L}}}$ and the shape and orientation of the ellipsoid. Now the relation between stress and strain rate in the grain and the matrix are related as

$$\dot{\underline{\underline{\sigma}}}^g = \dot{\underline{\underline{\sigma}}} + \underline{\underline{\mathbf{L}}}^* (\dot{\underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}} - \dot{\underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}}^g) \quad (15)$$

Using Eq.(14) in Eq.(15) we get

$$\dot{\underline{\underline{\sigma}}} = \underline{\underline{\mathbf{L}}}^g (\underline{\underline{\mathbf{L}}}^g + \underline{\underline{\mathbf{L}}}^*)^{-1} (\underline{\underline{\mathbf{L}}} + \underline{\underline{\mathbf{L}}}^*) \dot{\underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}} \quad (16)$$

$$\underline{\underline{\mathbf{L}}} = \langle \underline{\underline{\mathbf{L}}}^g (\underline{\underline{\mathbf{L}}}^g + \underline{\underline{\mathbf{L}}}^*)^{-1} (\underline{\underline{\mathbf{L}}} + \underline{\underline{\mathbf{L}}}^*) \rangle \quad (17)$$

Here $\langle \cdot \rangle$ represents the average taken over crystal orientations.

According to Berveiller-Zaoui (Berveiller and Zaoui, 1978) for isotropic elasticity, spherical inclusion and monotonic loading,

$$\underline{\underline{\sigma}}^g = \underline{\underline{\sigma}} + \mu\alpha(\underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}^p - \underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}^{pg}) \quad (18)$$

The concept behind all these approaches is to include corrective terms depending upon the plastic strain to compute local residual stresses. The linear dependency of this term concerning plastic strain gives higher values of stresses. The linear dependency of this term can be replaced by non-linear hardening variable and their dependency on the difference between local and global plastic strain called ' β rule' as proposed in (Cailletaud and Pilvin, 1994). The scale transition rule (' β rule') common to several homogenization schemes is as follows

$$\underline{\sigma}^g = \underline{\sigma} + \mu\alpha(\underline{\beta} - \underline{\beta}^g) \quad (19)$$

$$\underline{\beta} = \sum_{g=1}^N f^g \underline{\beta}^g, \quad \dot{\underline{\beta}} = \dot{\underline{\epsilon}}^{pg} - D\dot{\underline{\epsilon}}_{eq}^{pg} \underline{\beta}^g \quad (20)$$

where $\underline{\beta}^g$ is the nonlinear accommodation tensor, elastic isotropy is considered with shear modulus μ , $\dot{\underline{\epsilon}}_{eq}^{pg}$ is the norm of the mean plastic strain in each phase. The parameter D is calibrated such that the mean stress $\underline{\sigma}^g$ estimated in each phase is as close as to mean response of the corresponding grains within the polycrystalline aggregate computed via the finite element method. When $D = 0$, the model coincides with the Kröner's elastoplastic self-consistent scheme.

3.3. Full-field models

Full-field homogenization models predict the macroscopic response and microscopic field distribution in heterogeneous material based on the simulation of RVE (Böhm, 2004). The method is computationally expensive because it involves the solution of the boundary value problem which may contain a large number of degrees of freedom. The full-field models are accurate than the mean-field models and generally used as the reference models for the mean-field model predictions. The full-field models predict the local stress-strain fields and state variables throughout the microstructure which is a piece of important information for the damage prediction and localization problem. Several methods are available to predict the response of RVE. The most common methods are the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) (Moulinec and Suquet, 1998; Eyre, D. J. and Milton, G. W., 1999; Lebensohn, 2001a) and Finite Element Method (FEM) (Cailletaud et al., 2003b,a; Coudon et al., 2019; Flipon et al., 2020).

3.3.1. Homogenization using FEM

The first attempt to simulate polycrystal with FEM was carried out by Kalidindi et al. (1992); Bronkhorst et al. (1992). The model considered was the 2-D with each element representing each grain. The considered homogenization model was more like a mean-field model rather than the full-field model because the local field was missing and field in each grain was considered as constant hence was not able to model the strong deformation gradient usually seen in polycrystals. 3-D microstructure modeled with each grain representing several elements with regular mesh was presented by Mika and Dawson (1999). Finally, a more realistic microstructure with several elements per grain was modeled by Barbe et al. (2001).

The homogenization with FEM requires solving boundary value problems and for which mesh discretizing the geometry of the microstructure is necessary. The first approach sometimes called the multiphase element technique consists of superposing a regular 3-D mesh on the image of the microstructure as shown in Fig. 2(a). The drawback of this method is the poor description of interfaces. The proper meshing of the interfaces is possible with the second technique in the case of Voronoï polyhedra using standard 2-D and 3-D free meshing

Fig. 2: Two meshing techniques used for RVE (a) regular mesh (b) mesh representing grain boundaries

techniques as shown in Fig. 2(b). The application of boundary conditions to RVE is the main issue in full-field modeling. Four different types of boundary conditions are applied to RVE (Barbe et al., 2001; Cailletaud et al., 2003b; Segurado et al., 2018) (a) Periodic boundary conditions (b) statically uniform boundary conditions where applied surface tractions are homogeneous over RVE faces (c) kinematically uniform boundary conditions in which constant displacements are applied to the RVE boundary (d) mixed conditions combining uniform tractions and constant displacements on RVE surface. 2-D and 3-D polycrystalline aggregates with several grains can be generated via Voronoï tessellation as shown in Fig. 3.

It is also important to define the size of the RVE properly. The size of the RVE depends upon the studied properties (mechanical, thermal), phase morphology, and the boundary conditions. If the size of the RVE is too large can cause a tremendous amount of heterogeneity while the smaller size of the RVE is possible when a sufficient number of realizations of the microstructure is considered. The first attempt to define the size of the RVE can be found in Quilici et al. (1998).

3.3.2. Homogenization using FFT

The alternative to the homogenization using FEM is the numerical formulation based on the FFT method. An efficient FFT algorithm was originally proposed by (Moulinec and Suquet, 1994) to compute convolution integrals over the entire periodic RVE involving the periodic Green's function. The homogenization using FFT for the composites can be found in (Moulinec and Suquet, 1998; Eyre, D. J. and Milton, G. W., 1999; Michel et al., 1999) in which the source of heterogeneity in the spatial distribution of different phases with different mechanical properties. The homogenization using FFT for polycrystals can be found in (Lebensohn, 2001b; Grennerat et al., 2012; Eisenlohr et al., 2013) where the source of heterogeneity in the spatial distribution

Fig. 3: Crystallographic texture generated using Voronoi tessellation (a) 71 2-D grains (b) 432 2-D grains and (c) 150 3-D grains (Marchenko et al., 2016)

crystals with anisotropy.

4. Applications of polycrystal plasticity model

The accurate prediction of material properties using polycrystal homogenization requires the information of the microstructure of the material and the hardening behaviour. The microstructural properties can be easily obtained from the material characterization technique such as using the EBSD technique. The quantification of hardening behaviour can be done using micro-mechanical tests and multiscale modeling.

4.1. Determination of material strength

IN718 is a nickel-based superalloy having a wide range of applications in aerospace industries because of its good castability and weld- ability, high strength, and corrosion resistance. The determination of material properties with coupled experimental-simulation strategy is depicted in Fig. 4 (Cruzado et al., 2015). The microstructural information such as grain size distribution obtained from the material characterization technique can be easily translated to 3-D RVE using Voronoi tessellation. The single-crystal material parameters are obtained from the single crystal micro-pillar compression test as shown in Fig. 4.

The RVE used for the simulation is shown in Fig. 5(a). The periodic boundary condition is applied to 210-grain RVE. The grain size distribution is obtained from the experimental data. The average true stress vs. logarithmic strain curve of the uniaxial compression obtained from the experimental and the simulation is shown

Fig. 4: Coupled experimental-simulation approach to predict the mechanical properties of IN718 using polycrystal homogenization (Cruzado et al., 2015)

in Fig. 5(b). The agreement between them was fairly good: the maximum the difference in the compressive flow stress was below 4 %.

In the present study dislocation density-based model is used to calibrate the material parameters. The material parameters are calibrated from the experimental compression tests performed at different temperatures and strain rates using the Split-Hopkinson pressure bar (SHPB) test on IN718. The numerical simulations are performed with iso-volumetric and Voronoï polycrystals. The mesh used in the simulation is as shown in Fig. 2.

The flow rule in the visco-plastic framework, together with the classical Schmid law to trigger dislocation glide and also with kinematic hardening variable is given as

$$\dot{\gamma}^\alpha = \left\langle \frac{|\tau^\alpha| - \tau_c^\alpha}{K} \right\rangle^n \text{sign}(\tau^\alpha) \quad (21)$$

where τ^α is the resolved shear stress, τ_c^α is the isotropic hardening variable (CRSS). Higher value of power n and lower value of K lead to an almost ideal elastic-plastic behaviour in a given strain rate range.

Dislocation density based hardening rule is

$$\tau_c^\alpha = \tau_0 + \mu \sqrt{\sum_{u=1}^N a^{\alpha u} \rho^u} \quad (22)$$

Fig. 5: (a) RVE of polycrystalline IN718 showing finite element mesh (b) True stress-strain curve of uniaxial compression of IN718 by experimental test and polycrystal homogenization at room temperature. (Cruzado et al., 2015)

τ_0 is the initial critical resolved shear stress, $a^{\alpha u}$ is the interaction matrix, ρ^α is the adimensional dislocation density while (ρ^α/b^2) usual scalar dislocation density Evolution of dislocation density is given by:

$$\dot{\rho}^\alpha = |\dot{\gamma}^\alpha| (k_1^\alpha \sqrt{\rho^\alpha} - k_2^\alpha \rho^\alpha) \quad (23)$$

where k_1 coefficient related to dislocation storage, k_2 coefficient related to dislocation annihilation given by:

$$\frac{k_2^\alpha}{k_1^\alpha} = \frac{\chi b^\alpha}{g^\alpha} \left(1 - \frac{k T_{adiab}}{D^\alpha b^3} \ln \left(\frac{\dot{\epsilon}}{\dot{\epsilon}_0} \right) \right)$$

where k , ϵ_0 , g , D^α and χ are, respectively, Boltzmann's constant, a reference strain rate, effective activation energy, drag stress and interaction coefficient.

The internal heat generation (\dot{Q}_v) can be expressed as

$$\dot{Q}_v = \chi \dot{W}^p, \quad dW^p = \underline{\sigma} d\underline{\epsilon}^p, \quad \dot{\epsilon}^p = \sum_{\alpha=1}^N \dot{\gamma}^\alpha (\underline{m}^\alpha \otimes \underline{n}^\alpha) \quad (24)$$

where W^p is the plastic work and χ is the Taylor-Quinney parameter. Then temperature evolution is then given by

$$\dot{T}_{adiab} = \frac{\dot{Q}_v}{\rho c_p} \quad (25)$$

where ρ is the material density and c_p is the specific heat. The constitutive parameters used as an input in the numerical simulations are as summarised in Table 1. The optimized material parameters are as shown in Table 2 from the experimental stress-strain curve shown in Fig. 6.

4.2. Void growth in polycrystals

Ductile failure of polycrystal takes place due to void nucleation, growth, and coalescence (Thomason, 1993). Polycrystal homogenization models have been applied to study the effect of microstructural factors on the void growth using

Table 1: Optimized material parameters from the experimental stress-strain curve using polycrystal compression test

C_{11}	C_{12}	C_{44}	τ_0	n	K	k_1	g	D
259.6 GPa	179 GPa	109.6 GPa	145 MPa	8	20 MPa s ^{1/n}	3 × 10 ⁵ /mm	3	300 MPa
ρ_0^s	a_1	a_2	a_3	a_4	a_5	a_6		
1 × 10 ⁶ /mm ²	0.15	0.15	0.15	0.115	0.15	0.15		

Fig. 6: Identification of parameters from the experimental stress-strain curve at different temperature and strain rate for IN718 using Voronoi polycrystal

Table 2: Numerical values of the input material parameters used for the calibration of material parameters using polycrystal compression test

τ_0	n	K	k_1	g	D	a_1	a_2	a_3	a_4	a_5	a_6
145 MPa	8	20 MPa s ^{1/n}	3 × 10 ⁵ /mm	3	300 MPa	0.2	0.15	0.2	0.2	0.3	0.2

a dilatational viscoplastic FFT-based model. This approach was used to study void growth in damaged polycrystals under high-stress triaxiality ([Escobedo et al., 2011, 2013](#)).

4.3. Fatigue life

The localization of plastic strain in the slip band within the grain can be the origin of embryonic cracks. This process highly depends upon the material microstructure such as grain size and texture as well as the presence of defects (pores or inclusions). Therefore microstructure plays an important role in fatigue and the link between microstructure and fatigue life can be possible by simulations. The microstructure-sensitive computational modeling of fatigue can be found in [McDowell and Dunne \(2010\)](#); [Pineau et al. \(2016\)](#).

4.4. Other applications

The use of Directionally Solidified (DS) alloys, for instance, nickel-based superalloys have been increased tremendously in the past decade in aerospace applications for the components operating at high temperatures such as turbine blades ([Vladimirov et al., 2009](#); [Chen et al., 2013](#)). The grain orientation and morphology of the material are crucial in component design. The effect of elastic and plastic heterogeneities of Nickel-based superalloy using the multiscale scheme can be found in [Martin et al. \(2014\)](#). The contribution of elastic and plastic anisotropy is calibrated from the full-field model and included in the mean-field model. The statistical effects of grain boundaries on the turbine blade using full-field models for columnar grains can be found in [Coudon et al. \(2020\)](#). The effect of grain size and grain size ratio between ultrafine grains and coarse grains on the local and global mechanical response using full-field models in bimodal polycrystals is demonstrated in [Flipon et al. \(2020\)](#).

5. Concluding remark

Computational homogenization is a powerful tool to predict the mechanical response of the polycrystalline aggregate taking into account the microstructure of the material. The polycrystal homogenization links the microstructure of the material with the mechanical response which is not possible by the classical crystal plasticity models. Nowadays the computational homogenization approach is being widely accepted by the industries for instance aerospace and automotive to analyze the mechanical behavior of polycrystalline aggregates ([Roters et al., 2010](#); [Coudon et al., 2020](#)). The industrial usage of the computational homogenization of polycrystal is supported by the open-source software packages that can be used to represent the microstructure of polycrystals, for instance, Dream.3-D and Neper to generate 2-D and 3-D grains.

The polycrystals subjected to large deformation does not only undergo shape change but also the grain fragmentation and recrystallization processes which lead to dramatic microstructural changes. This information is essential for thermo-mechanical processes to manufacture materials with new properties and microstructures. This can be achieved with coupled application polycrystal homogenization with phase-field modeling ([Abrivard et al., 2012](#); [Güvenç et al., 2014](#)).

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